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6. Introduction

The process of state building in the 21st century is one of the most challenging tasks in the face of post conflict societies. It is about establishing the ability of institutions to impose authority, deliver services, and manage resources over a defined territory (Fukuyama, 2004; Weber, 1946). The military as an institution bears upon issues of subordination and rationalization of the violence monopoly and attempts at creating conversion when it comes to transforming armed movements into professional national defense forces (Bryden & Hänggi, 2005).

South Sudan offers an important case study. By becoming the world's youngest sovereign state in 2011, South Sudan inherited the former rebel group known as the SPLA (Sudan People's Liberation Army), which turned the tides as the South Sudan People's Defense Force (SSPDF). However, within two years, the country plunged into a civil war inevitably tearing its fragile institutional framework and flouting the basic question about the military's role in state-building (Nyadera, 2018).

This is what prompted this investigation-the paradox that the military of South Sudan is still institutionally competitive, ethnically confederated, and embodied in patronage systems despite the significant financial resources put into Security Sector Reform (SSR) and Disarmament, Demobilization, and Reintegration (DDR) (Warner, 2016; de Waal, 2016). The study intends to examine the roles of military institutions in governance, institutional development, and political settlements in South Sudan, focusing on the period from the Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA, 2005) to the present-day activities under the Revitalized Agreement (R-ARCSS, 2018–present). As a single case study situated in a post-conflict context, the research will analyze how military institutions have shaped state-building processes, identifying the conditions under which they act as supportive agents or as hindrances. While the design is not comparative, relevant lessons from other African

experiences—such as Tanzania’s military reforms following the 1964 mutiny, or developments in Rwanda and the Democratic Republic of Congo—may be drawn upon in the discussion and analysis where they provide useful insights. In addition, lessons from Uganda’s military trajectory—particularly the evolution of the Uganda People’s Defence Force (UPDF) and its role in governance and post-conflict state consolidation—offer valuable perspectives that can enrich the understanding of South Sudan’s case.

6.1. Background to the study:

The study in focus highlights state building in South Sudan—an activity that its proponents associate with the creation of capacities for enforcing authority, producing public goods, and maintaining order in a territorially bounded space (Fukuyama 2004; Weber 1946; Rotberg 2004). Nation building—the creation of shared identity and social solidarity (Anderson 1983; Wimmer 2018)—is complementary in essence, while this study argues that, before any nation building could deliver its fruits, it was necessary to establish functional institutions with particular reference to security institutions (Fukuyama 2004; Jok 2012). South Sudan’s experience shows that lack of state institutions rather than failed identity has been the primary source of instability, especially—as the 2013 civil war demonstrated—time and again, when political competition was viewed and therefore conducted in terms of military factions rather than mostly institutional set of mechanisms (Nyadera 2018).

The military is taken as the focal institution of analysis in this framework. In post-conflict settings, the military is often seen as the most organized and resourced of institutions, thus shaping governance and the political economy (Bryden & Hänggi, 2005; Tilly, 1985). Throughout the struggle, the SPLA/SSPDF has essentially functioned as a proto-state, assuming authority, collecting resources, and social services during the entire era of the

liberation war (LeRiche, 2018). Now, as time-employed in an opportunity beyond security operation, resource control, mobilization for ethnicity, and political settlement, the military becomes an important aspect in explaining state-building outcomes (de Waal, 2015; Jok, 2012; Usmonov, 2022). Developing through the institutional dynamics of the military, this research averts further light on the main question of why South Sudan has failed in consolidating a functional state inspite of specific international support and internal articulations.

State-building in post-conflict contexts has also often depended on the reshaping and professionalization of the military. Bosnia, Kosovo, Afghanistan, and Iraq demonstrate various promises and obstacles with regard to these efforts. It is critically important to unite disparate militias under a single national umbrella, promoting stability in the short term and also nurturing institutions in the long term, while containing established patronage networks that degrade organizational cohesion (Paris 2004; Chandler 2006; Menkhaus 2006). Success leads directly to military reform, which subsequently serves as the states' building block; failure makes the entire state vulnerable.

At a global level, Bosnia and Herzegovina does represent a successful case of post-conflict military reforms ever since the Dayton Peace Accords in 1995. The country was faced with the challenge of uniting ethnically divided armies and the result was the integration of forces into a single continuous national military structure with democratic control, thus ending the existence of parallel structures and standardizing the recruitment and promotion rates to preclude domination by any one ethnicity (Paris, 2004). These reforms, meeting European military standards, aided in the professionalization of the Armed Forces of Bosnia and Herzegovina (AFBiH). It transformed the once very credible military into an institution that was, above all, welcomed and trusted across the ethnic lines. The success of this transformation was evidenced through different international sojourns: involvement in peacekeeping operations in Iraq, Afghanistan, and even under the UN (Menkhaus, 2006). This significant

transformation made the military very much a key stone in state-building, symbolizing the unity of the nation and root of legitimacy for the Bosnian state.

In Africa, the Tanzania of Julius Nyerere offers another riveting case. The Tanzania People's Defence Force (TPDF) was consentsized to be professional and maintain civilian oversight. No ethnic domination was allowed in recruiting, the armed forces being one of the components of a united nation. The TPDF provided defense for sovereignty, participated in social programs, and helped to preserve unity across its heterogeneous society. The cofounding of military reform with visionary leadership and inclusive governance illustrates the possibility that armed forces can be the means for stability and state building, rather than conditions for fragmentation.

By contrast, state-building efforts in independent South Sudan reveal how military institutions have functioned less as instruments of consolidation and more as vehicles of elite competition, ethnic mobilization, and resource plunder. During the liberation struggle, the SPLA operated as a proto-state, collecting taxes and administering rudimentary justice (LeRiche, 2018). However, post-CPA reforms were undermined by the ill-planned integration of over 200,000 troops, which produced fragmentation and conflicting command loyalties (Warner, 2016). Political competition translated into military confrontation, and the absence of professionalism and civilian oversight left ethnic militias at the center of the 2013 crisis (Jok, 2012; Watson, 2016). The 2015 peace agreement sought to unify forces but was quickly undermined by factionalism and narrow political incentives (Bior, 2018). As South Sudan's trajectory demonstrates, military reform remains central to state-building, yet the lack of inclusivity, professionalism, and accountability has perpetuated instability despite international support and internal articulations.

6.2. Statement of the Problem

In classical state-formative theory, the monopoly of legitimate violence is supposed to be the basis of sovereign statehood. In the case of South Sudan, the military should evolve into a professional, cohesive, and politicized alien national institution through its transformation into a peace that will ensure a sustainable transition from post-conflict. Ideally, the South Sudan People's Defence Forces (SSPDF) would provide security under civilian authority, recruit on merit rather than ethnicity, and serve as the foundation for constitutional development, economic growth, and democratic consolidation (Huntington, 1957; Bryden & Hänggi, 2005).

Practically, all are agreed that, as regards its military, South Sudan remains a fragmented and politicized institution. By demanding the "open-door" integration policy, those forces expanded their numbers towards the 200,000 mark, hence creating parallel chains of command and undermining any coherence and harmony within their centralized structure (Warner, 2016). Recruitment and promotion follow ethnic lines, particularly the Dinka–Nuer divide, turning the military into a vehicle for ethnic mobilization rather than national integration (Jok, 2012; Nyadera, 2018). The SSPDF operates within de Waal's (2015) "political marketplace," where military positions are traded for access to resources, checkpoints, and commercial ventures. Officers occupy civilian posts, blurring military-civilian boundaries and weakening oversight. Security Sector Reform (SSR) initiatives have repeatedly failed, not due to technical shortcomings but because elites benefit from unreformed structures and resist change (Watts et al., 2022; Bior, 2018).

This institutional hybridity creates a paradox: the very institution meant to consolidate the state has become the primary driver of its collapse (Watson, 2016). Elite competition translates directly into military conflict, as seen in the 2013 and 2016 civil wars (Nyadera, 2018). The SSPDF has perpetrated violence against civilians, eroding the social contract and forcing reliance on UN peacekeepers for protection (Johnson, 2019). Oil wealth fuels elite competition rather than financing state-building, while predatory military behavior entrenches food

insecurity and displacement (Ashaba et al., 2019; Okuk, 2023). Without transformation, South Sudan risks permanent fragility and cyclical violence.

Despite extensive scholarship on South Sudan's political history, critical gaps remain. Existing studies focus on elite-level bargaining (Kiir vs. Machar) but neglect mid-level commanders, rank-and-file perceptions, and the informal patronage structures shaping military behavior. There is limited analysis of the political economy of military-commercial networks and insufficient comparative work explaining why military transformation succeeded in contexts like Tanzania but failed in South Sudan. This research addresses these gaps through a longitudinal analysis of SPLA/SSPDF evolution (2005–present), integrating Weberian state theory, Tilly's war-making framework, neo-patrimonialism, and political marketplace theory.

6.3 Objectives

General Objective

To critically examine the role that military institutional dynamics have played on the state-building process in the Republic of South Sudan, focusing on a transformation process from a liberation movement to a professional national defence force.

Specific Objectives

The following specific objectives will form part of the total aim of this study:

1. To assess the institutional transition of the South Sudan People's Defence Forces (SSPDF) from an ethno-political militia structure toward a professionalized, non-partisan national army.
2. To investigate the influence of military officials on civilian governance and policymaking at both the national and state levels in South Sudan.

3. To investigate the role of military-linked commercial interests in South Sudan's political economy and their impact on state revenue centralization.

Research Questions

1. To what extent has the SSPDF transitioned from an ethno-political militia structure into a unified, professional national military institution?
2. How do military commanders influence civilian governance and policy-making at both the national and state levels in South Sudan?
3. In what ways do military-linked commercial interests shape South Sudan's political economy, and how do they affect state revenue centralization?

6.4 Significance of the Study

This research makes important contributions to theory, methodology, and policy in understanding the role of the military in state-building in South Sudan.

The study contributes to the historical social science on militarised state-building when classic readings on state formation (reading of Weber 1946; Tilly 1985) are integrated with contemporary neo-patrimonialism political-marketplace, and hybrid governance frameworks (de Waal 2015; Bachmann 2024). Being an extension of Tilly's war-making and state-making matrix, allowing for the case when war-making does not entirely merge the state but fragment it, this project provides new insight into how national liberation movements are transformed—or fail to give birth to fully functional national institutions. Also, by showing the reasons why SSR standard models fail when the military is entrenched in political settlements and patronage networks, this research enhances the debate about SSR.

This study employs a qualitative multi-case study design, including elite interviews under Chatham House Rules, document analysis of peace agreements and military policies, and comparative case studies. The mixed-methods approach is of particular utility in conflict-

affected settings because access to military and political elites is limited, while the sensitive nature of the information sought almost prevents real, rigorous knowledge from being generated.

Through triangulation with interviews from various sources, document sources, and contextual information, the study argues that military institutions are capable of being studied empirically under conditions of fragility. This exercise greatly improves the validity of the findings and provides the anatomy for the standard method of instruction in further studies focusing on military politicians within post-conflict transitions in attempts to stimulate methodological considerations within the domains of political science and conflict studies.

Discovered findings will definitely have some influence on the security sector reform program, peacebuilding interventions and governance support in South Sudan and related settings. If the impediments to military transformation such as ethnicized recruitment, patronage-driven command structures, and military-commercial networks are identified, an input required from international donors, policymakers, and civil society to make these triggers unblocking in progression towards peace. It does specifically point out the need for politically-based changes that go beyond technical training and capacity-building to solve the root causes of militarization. At the national level, the study bears potential relevance for the South Sudanese actors in civil society, the political terrain, and ordinary citizens, by clarifying how military control works toward undermining governance and security, thus providing more clout to the national advocacy for the submission military under civilian oversight and for demanding accountability.

6.5 Scope of the Study

This study attempts to analyse South Sudan's military transformation and state-building from the Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA, 2005) through independence in 2011, the civil war

of 2013, and the Revitalized Agreement (R-ARCSS, 2018-present). Geographically, it is concerned with Juba as a political and military core but offers additional insights into the state capitals like Malakal, Wau, and Bentiu for peripheral dynamics to be captured. There are other objectives of being analytical in practice and confronting traditional histories or ethnographic detail to glimpse a different angle-namely, to argue for the compelling analytical value military actors and institutions bring to shaping state-building outcomes in this most recent nation.

6.7 Literature Review

The review is a critical synthesis of the scholarship that focuses on military engrossment in state-building endeavors, with South Sudan as a precise case in the larger context of African post-conflict experiences. It is theoretically organized around the key question: "How is South Sudan's military involved in its state-building processes?" By demarcating the outline to consider, possibly, three main dimensions: (1) institutional transformation of the military, (2) civil-military studies, and (3) political economic debates on control and links with militarization. The review is designed to be an interface for the ongoing search for theories, empirical data, and gaps that have not engaged researchers thus far.

Theoretical Conceptions of the State and Military Institutions

The contribution of the military to the process of state formation has been incorporated into the classical theory of the formation of the state. Weber (1946) defines the state as an entity that manages the "monopoly of the legitimate use of physical force in its territory," meaning that the military is the institutionalized form of force with which the predominant interest is defended. Similarly, Huntington (1957) sees the military as an institution, professional, expert, responsible, and corporate. Together, these frameworks have profoundly shaped international approaches to Security Sector Reform (SSR), which assume that post-conflict militaries should

evolve toward Weberian-Huntingtonian ideals of professionalization (Bryden & Hänggi, 2005).

Africanist scholars have continually disputed the universal applicability of these Western frames of reference. Herbst (2000) argued that the African making of the state diverges coherently from the ways the Europeans created their state because of the international-colonial bound/rule border-created weak institutionalization and the emergence of international norms against territorial conquests. Regarding the colonial state, Mamdani (1996) drew attention to the bifurcation of the military institutions; unlike European colonial states, which were designed to protect colonial frontiers, the African colonial military was intended to deracinate the population with intelligence systems based on territorial recognition and acknowledging loyalty for territorial integrity. More recently, Bachmann (2024) explains his understanding of so-called “quasi-armies,” referring to the concept of the military institutions that have been fusing conventional military characteristics with the more informal killing characteristics of militias, patronage networks, and ethnic mobilizing mechanisms. These critiques hint at the fact that the military institutions in Africa more than often operate in hybrid governance systems, with formal structures existing parallel with loyalty, patronage, and ethnicity practices.

South Sudan exemplifies these critiques. The Sudan People’s Liberation Army (SPLA) originated as a rebel movement rather than a state institution, functioning as a proto-state during the liberation struggle by administering justice, collecting taxes, and mobilizing communities (Johnson, 2016; LeRiche, 2018). Transformation into the South Sudan People's Defence Force (SSPDF) after independence was characterized by competing, fragmented nepotistic command structures, politicized recruitment, and fuzziness of boundaries between military, economic, and political spheres (Warner 2016). Integration systems expanded the number of forces to over

200,000 in personnel strength, thus undermining coherence and resulting in parallel chains of command (Warner 2016).

South Sudan's experience demonstrates how liberation armies often defy Weberian expectations of professionalization. Instead of consolidating statehood through a monopoly of legitimate violence, the SSPDF has become a fragmented institution embedded in patronage and ethnic networks. This reflects the Africanist critique that state-building in post-conflict Africa cannot be understood solely through Western models of military professionalization. Rather, it requires analysis of hybrid governance, where military institutions serve simultaneously as instruments of coercion, vehicles of ethnic mobilization, and actors in the political economy.

By contrasting Weberian definitions of the state with Africanist perspectives on hybrid governance, this study situates South Sudan within broader debates on militarized state-building. It argues that the failure of the SSPDF to transform into a professional national institution is not simply a technical shortcoming but a structural outcome of historical legacies, political economy incentives, and governance patterns that reward armed mobilization over institutional consolidation.

Political Economy of Military-Linked Resource Control

The interplay between natural resource wealth and state formation have been extensively theorized from paradigms of the "resource curse" and rentier state. Drawing on examples from the works of Karl (1997) and Ross (2001), it is posited that oil revenues often have a negative impact on institutional development, as they allow elites to escape taxation and thereby affect the capacity of the fiscal contract between state and citizens. Beblawi and Luciani (1987) explain that when resource wealth relies on external rent rather than domestic income, it reduces the motivation to build accountability and robust institutions. In these situations,

natural resource wealth becomes a source of patronage for elites rather than the sustainable foundation for state capacity.

South Sudan exemplifies this dynamic. With over 95% of government revenue derived from oil, the state has relied on resource rents to sustain military patronage and elite competition rather than investing in institutional development (Patey, 2010; Ashaba et al., 2019). Oil wealth has entrenched militarized governance, as revenues are channelled into expanding the armed forces, rewarding loyalty, and financing factional competition. This undermines the creation of a social contract, as citizens are excluded from fiscal participation and accountability mechanisms.

According to Waal, the theory of Political Marketplace Theory (2015) serves as a critical tool for understanding the intertwined resource wealth and militarization in politics. Loyalty is said to be traded—primarily through wealth and status. In South Sudan, military ranks are tradeable items and are offered on the table for negotiating with the elites. The commander gets control of checkpoints, binding commercial taxes, and the commercial enterprises, effectively inserting themselves into ever-more 'elite' dialogue resistant from any economic reform (UN Security Council, 2018). Transactional logic helps explain the multiple defections, inflated military grades, and repeated peace agreement implosions as the realignment of loyalty insider deals, which oneself is changed with the financial streams.

The resource curse view underlines the fundamental problem of oil dependency so that it may have a sequential nature in relation to resource rent affecting institutional vulnerability. The political market hypothesis provides greater nuance by demonstrating how the resource rent is actively mobilized by elites to strengthen militarized patron-client networks. In South Sudan, oil revenues have not simply weakened institutions; they have financed the militarization of

governance. This has resulted in the SSPDF becoming both a coercive force and economic operator.

From the above literature, it is apparent that we can concentrate on the SSPDF as a military institution and a primary player in South Sudan's political economy. The power dynamics stretching far beyond the confines of resource curse theory will simultaneously be explained through the political marketplace perspective when issues concerning the role of military-encumbered business activities of SSPEPs are so much in themselves the likes of control of checkpoints and taxation and the appropriation of oil revenues.

Institutions versus Identity

A vibrant debate pinpointing whether or not the failure of nation-building lies more with weak institutions or with severe ethnic divide is in place-right in the middle of discussion in both political science and conflict research.

Institutionalist interpretation does not believe that institutional weakness results in restraining the elites from manipulating political and economic systems for personal gain. According to North (1990) and Acemoglu and Robinson (2012), weaknesses in institutions lead to rent-seeking opportunities, break down the rule of law, and erode state capacity. For them, ethnic mobilization arises from institutional weakness: when rules either vanish or are simply ignored, elite elites leverage identity divisions in the consolidation of their power.

Identity-based theories, on the other hand, focus on an ethnic division as the key driver of conflict. Horowitz (1985) and Posen (1993) affirm that ethnic identities, when politicized, create deep cleavages, which guide political competitions and military fragmentation alike. In South Sudan, the Dinka–Nuer split has articulated itself into rivaling political factions and alliances, leading often to cycles of violence and the undoing of efforts at forging a stable nation (Nyadera, 2018; Watson, 2016).

Mahmood Mamdani's (1996) bifurcated state framework offers a synthesis that transcends this dichotomy. Mamdani demonstrates how colonial governance institutionalized ethnicity through indirect rule, embedding fragmentation into state structures. Applied to South Sudan, this framework explains how ethnic divisions are not merely primordial identities but are politically constructed and institutionalized within governance practices. Recruitment, command structures, and political competition are thus shaped by historically embedded ethnic fragmentation (Mamdani, 2018).

The literature suggests that weak institutions and ethnic mobilization are not mutually exclusive explanations but mutually reinforcing dynamics. Institutional weakness incentivizes elites to mobilize ethnic loyalties, while ethnic fragmentation undermines institutional coherence. In South Sudan, this cycle is evident in the SSPDF, where recruitment and promotion often occur along ethnic lines, and military factions align with political leaders from their communities. This dynamic perpetuates militarized governance and obstructs efforts at professionalization and reform.

Institutional and identity-based theories are relevant but essentially treat institutions and identity as independent and uninterlaced variables. However, available data on South Sudan imply that the opposite is true: the institutional fragility creates conditions for ethnic mobilization, which in turn weakens institutional coherence. It really is a combination of the institutional breakdown and political identity that sustains military rule and cycles of conflict. Therefore, it is not the mere technocratic failure or socio-political cleavage which has led to the failure of state building in South Sudan. A more comprehensive analysis is required, including the global political economy of weak institutions and militarized patronage, which takes into account how ethnic mobilization is situated within such a framework.

Critical Evaluation and Synthesis

The literature on South Sudan's state-building and military transformation reveals a complex interplay of institutional fragility, ethnic mobilization, and political economy incentives. Scholars broadly agree that the failure of military transformation cannot be reduced to technical deficits alone; rather, it reflects deeper structural and political dynamics. The two sides of their argument show different priorities their research findings have different limits and unresolved issues persist between them.

Institutional Transformation of the Military Classical theorists such as Weber (1946) and Huntington (1957) argue that the state consolidates authority through a monopoly of legitimate violence and a professionalized military institution. Their frameworks underpin international approaches to Security Sector Reform (SSR), which assume that post-conflict militaries should evolve toward Weberian-Huntingtonian ideals of expertise, responsibility, and corporateness (Bryden & Hänggi, 2005). However, Africanist scholars challenge these assumptions. Herbst (2000) emphasizes the divergence of African state-making from European trajectories due to colonial boundaries and weak institutionalization, while Mamdani (1996) highlights the bifurcated colonial state that embedded ethnic fragmentation into military institutions. Bachmann (2024) further introduces the notion of "quasi-armies," describing hybrid military institutions that combine conventional features with militia characteristics and patronage networks.

South Sudan exemplifies these critiques. The SPLA started as a rebel group which operated as a quasi-government organization that maintained order through its judicial system and helped communities to organize their activities (Johnson, 2016; LeRiche, 2018). The SSPDF emerged from its transformation because the organization established divided command systems which controlled who joined the military while creating different military and political and economic divisions (Warner, 2016). The integration policies increased force size to more than 200000 military members who created multiple command systems which disrupted operational unity.

The evidence indicates that South Sudan military transformation failed because historical governance practices which promote military recruitment created structural problems which developed into military problems. What is missing, however, is sustained empirical analysis of how these hybrid practices operate at sub-national levels and within everyday military life.

Political Economy of Military-Linked Resource Control Resource curse theorists such as Karl (1997) and Ross (2001) argue that oil revenues undermine institutional development by allowing elites to bypass taxation, weakening the fiscal contract between state and citizens. Beblawi and Luciani (1987) similarly describe rentier states as reliant on external rents, reducing incentives for accountability. In South Sudan, with over 95% of government revenue derived from oil, resource rents have sustained military patronage and elite competition rather than institutional development (Patey, 2010; Ashaba et al., 2019).

De Waal's (2015) Political Marketplace Theory adds nuance by conceptualizing political power as transactional, where loyalty is purchased through financial and positional rewards. Evidence from South Sudan shows military positions commodified as bargaining chips, with commanders controlling checkpoints, taxation, and commercial ventures (UN Security Council, 2018). This transactional logic explains recurrent defections, inflated ranks, and the collapse of peace agreements. While resource curse theory highlights structural dependence, it often assumes linear causality. What is missing is systematic mapping of military-commercial networks and their precise impact on state revenue centralization.

Identities versus Institutions Identity institution theories argue that weak institutions allow the powerful to take rents, which kills the state. In this perspective, ethnic mobilization emerges as a symptom of institutional decay. Meanwhile, identity theories emphasize that—imaging ethnically configured conflict—these dividing lines are created politics, which will go on forever (Horowitz, 1985; Posen 1993). In South Sudan, the Dinka-Nuer divide has consistently

shaped political rivalries and military alliances that have flung the country into cycles of violence (Nyadera, 2018; Watson, 2016).

Mamdani's (1996, 2018) bifurcated state framework synthesizes these perspectives, showing how colonial governance institutionalized ethnicity within state structures. Applied to South Sudan, this framework explains how ethnic fragmentation is embedded in recruitment, command structures, and political competition. There is a common argument in literature that institutions and ethnization interact in a continuous fashion: institutional weakness nurtures ethnic loyalty but while ethnic fragmentation weakens institution framework. What is missing is systematic application of integrative frameworks like Mamdani's to South Sudan, and empirical research on how these dynamics play out at local levels of governance and within the SSPDF's everyday practices.

Synthesis

Across these themes, scholars converge on the view that South Sudan's military transformation failure reflects structural legacies, political economy incentives, and governance patterns that reward armed mobilization over institutional consolidation. Yet, existing studies remain limited in scope. They focus heavily on elite-level bargains in Juba, neglecting sub-national experiences and micro-level dynamics within the SSPDF. Resource curse analyses assume linear relationships without mapping military-commercial networks. Comparative studies always remain descriptive without explaining the divergent reform trajectories across different African contexts. Finally, the application of integrative frameworks like Mamdani's bifurcated state has never been systemically applied to South Sudan's military transformation.

This study brings together institutional analysis, civil-military topics, and political economy explanatory perspectives in a grand whole.. In doing so, it contributes both theoretically—by

extending state-building models to contexts of fragmentation—and practically—by generating evidence-based recommendations for SSR and governance reform in South Sudan.

Identifying the Gap

The literature on South Sudan's state-building and military transformation has generated valuable insights into the interplay of institutions, identity, and political economy. Scholars such as Johnson (2014) highlighted the complex nature of the CPA, in contrast to Mamdani (2018) who criticized the structural explanation of the Transitional Governance Agenda as he thought it had entrenched the ethnic fragmentation. Resource curse theorists like Karl (1997), Ross (2001), and so forth draw attention to the dangerous repercussions of oil dependence. De Waal (2015) goes further and suggests that resource rents sustain militarized patronage through Political Marketplace Theory.. Studies of civil-military relations (Jok, 2012; Nyadera, 2018) document elite-level militarization, and comparative analyses (Albrecht & Jackson, 2009; Eriksson Baaz & Verweijen, 2013) provide contrasts with other African contexts. Institutionalist and identity-based theories (North, 1990; Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012; Horowitz, 1985; Posen, 1993) further enrich the debate, though often treated as separate explanatory lenses.

Despite valuable contributions, the literature remains limited in scope. Most existing studies focus heavily on national-level elite bargains in Juba, neglecting how state-building attempts are experienced at the sub-national level. Rarely have the perspectives of local government actors, mid-level commanders, and rank-and-file soldiers been explored to shed light on how militarized governance is sustained in everyday practices. Resource curse analyses often assume linear relationships without mapping the military-commercial networks that channel oil rents into patronage. Comparative research on the other hand, descriptively states each side, but does not offer explanatory or predictive knowledge as to why the reform trajectory, or lack

of it in some cases, seems to differ diametrically from one country to another in Africa. Finally, integrative analytical frameworks such as the bifurcated state, as named by Mamdani, have not been invoked systematically in the case of South Sudan's military transformation.

This thesis fills that gap by moving beyond elite-level analysis to investigate how state-building and military transformation are experienced at the sub-national level—for example, in local governance contexts such as Wau or Malakal. In order to bridge institutional, identity, and political economy approaches, this study provides a multilevel analysis by integrating perspectives from mid-level commanders, rank-and-file soldiers, and local institutions.

Theoretical Framework

The study considers the Weberian Bureaucracy Theory as its analytical method and focuses on military involvement in state-building in South Sudan. According to Weber (1946), the state should maintain stability in the sense that the state claims an exclusive right to exercise legitimate violence within the boundaries of its control and suggests the need for a bureaucratic organization as a tool of effective institutions, with main themes of hierarchy, legal-rational authority, merit-based recruitment, and rule-governed function. Basically, the application of Weber's theory on military institutions suggests that professionalization, a chain of command, and obedience to civil authorities are crucial in statehood construction.

In the South Sudanese context, Weber's paradigm provides an explanation from which the Sudan People's Liberation Army (SPLA) and its successor, the South Sudan People's Defence Force (SSPDF), can be measured. It is seen that the heavy reliance on patronage, ethnic mobilization, and fragmented command structures signifies an outright deviation from Weberian ideals of rational-legal order. Therefore, the Theory of Bureaucracy can be useful with respect to the normative or prescriptive model as well as the diagnostic tool, which can

admit how military institutions have not transformed into professional state-building instruments in South Sudan.

Weber's Bureaucracy Theory serves as essential framework which helps researchers examine both institutional structure and organizational change. The system establishes its evaluation standard through three components which include hierarchical organization, rule-based operational methods and systems that reward merit-based achievement (Weber 1978). The theory demonstrates its fundamental value through its examination of rational-legal authority which shows how civilian control and established command systems serve as essential components for constructing democratic governments. The framework provides universal applicability which enables researchers to evaluate security sector reform efforts from different countries by using Bosnia and Herzegovina as a case study of military integration and professionalization which occurred through international assistance (Chandler 2006 Paris 2004).

However, this theory also carries significant limitations when applied to fragile post-colonial settings. Its low sensitivity to informal authorities and patronage networks tends to deny the realities of countries like South Sudan where militarized patronage and resource dependency, especially on oil revenues, shape institutional behaviour (Rolandsen, 2015). Weber's natural inclination toward excluding identity politics, therefore, leaves him devoid of insight on how ethnic mobilization and factionalism affect military institutions in divided societies (Young, 2012). Moreover, his doctrinal stance that institutional development follows a linear path completely ignores hybrid governance systems, where formal and informal modes of administration coexist and often work to undermine the principles of bureaucratic governance (Menkhaus, 2006). These weaknesses point to the need for compensating Weber's model with context-sensitive approaches in the analysis of military reform in fragile states.

By adopting Weber's Bureaucracy Theory, this study situates South Sudan's military transformation within a tradition that emphasizes rational-legal authority and professionalization (Weber, 1946). However, the limitations of Weber's model—particularly its Eurocentric assumptions—necessitate supplementation with Africanist critiques and political economy perspectives. Mamdani's bifurcated state highlights how colonial governance embedded ethnic fragmentation into institutions (Mamdani, 1996), while de Waal's Political Marketplace explains how loyalty and military positions are traded through patronage and resource rents (de Waal, 2015). This inter-theoretical approach enables the research to evaluate the SSPDF against Weberian ideals while also explaining why, in practice, patronage, ethnicity, and oil rents have undermined opportunities for professionalization and state-building in South Sudan (Nyadera, 2018; Warner, 2016).

7. Methodology

The methodology section is the “engine room” of the thesis. It explains the conduct of the research and also justifies why such methods were chosen over others. The chapter delineates how data will be collected and analysed to respond to the research questions posed by the study.

Research Philosophy

This study subscribes to Interpretivism as its guiding philosophy, given its qualitative multiple case study design. Ontologically, interpretivism takes the view that reality is indeed multiple and socially constructed; whereas, epistemologically, the emphasis remains on the meanings and ways in which those meanings derive from individual lived experiences as being the locus of knowledge (Creswell, 2013; Morgan, 2007)-a spectroscopic, exhaustive, power-intensive politic of potential researches across different pending. This makes it particularly appropriate for a post-conflict context like South Sudan, where institutional dynamics are largely shaped by perceptions, narrative, and lived realities of people rather than purely by structural or legal frameworks.

In contrast, positivism is renowned for endorsing a single level: objectivity and measurability through universal laws, thus developing generalization and prediction capabilities. Such an apparatus is limited in delicate settings considering that personal responses are central to understanding institutional behavior, whereas the perspective of interpretivism, due to its immense depth and human meaning, throws up a sturdier platform from which this pre-study is sought to become a reality. Pragmatism, on the other hand, is appreciated for being another side, aiming at the practical solution to research problems and helping method selection by practicality (Creswell, 2018; Morgan, 2007). This Pragmatism fortifies interpretivism by way of methodological flexibility, including ways in which the study could adjust to the milieu of

the research carried out in post-conflict South Sudan—elite interviews, document analysis, and comparative case studies.

Research Design

The study will adopt an Exploratory design within a Qualitative Multiple Case Study framework. An exploratory design fits the present research, which seeks to uncover how military institutions have influenced state-building outcomes – not simply in terms of demonstrating an evolution history. This design cuts very closely to the overall goal of examining the liberation movement transition into an SSPDF professional defense force.

Case study research is deemed appropriate because complex social phenomena should be examined in the 'real-world' contexts where the divisions between the phenomena and their environments blur (Stake, 2006). Many case studies are conducted at both national and subnational levels (Greater Upper Nile, Greater Bahr el Ghazal, Greater Equatoria), allowing comparative studies to be made with respect to an array of actors and processes, notwithstanding differences of ethnicity, economy, and conflict situations. While not generalizable, the exculpatory case study offers rich contextual and methodological insights that contextualize the research inquiry into militarization, reforming institutions, and the study of statehood, i.e., in the extent necessary for the study's research objectives and research questions.

Research Approach

This study adopts a qualitative research approach to investigate how military institutional dynamics have shaped state-building in South Sudan. An exploratory approach is appropriate because the subject matter—military transformation from a liberation movement to a professional defense force—remains under-researched, particularly at sub-national levels.

Rather than testing predetermined hypotheses, the study seeks to uncover patterns, generate insights, and build explanations about how patronage, ethnicity, and resource rents influence military institutions and state-building outcomes.

Population and Sampling

The study is conducted across multiple sites to capture both national dynamics and subnational variation. The **primary site** is Juba, the center of national government and military headquarters. **Secondary sites** include Greater Upper Nile (e.g., Malakal/Bentiu), Greater Bahr el Ghazal (e.g., Wau), and Greater Equatoria (e.g., Torit/Yei), each chosen for their distinct ethnic, economic, and conflict patterns. The target population includes active and retired SSPDF officers, civilian officials at national and state levels, peace process actors (RJMEC, CTSAMVM, international guarantors), civil society leaders, journalists, academic analysts, and international actors such as UN agencies and SSR partners.

Sampling employs **purposive and snowball techniques**, guided by criterion and maximum variation strategies (Patton, 2015). With qualitative research, sample size is determined by saturation, the point where collecting data brings up no new themes. Anticipated sample sizes include approximately 30–35 military officers, 20–25 civilian officials, 10–15 peace process actors, 15–20 civil society leaders and experts, and 5–10 international actors.

Data Collection Methods

Primary data will be collected through **semi-structured interviews** and **focus group discussions (FGDs)**.

Key Intelligence Interpretations (KII): Participants in the KIIs are expected to be those who have inside information and involvement with either military or governance structures in South

Sudan. Naturally, this group will include high-ranking and medium commanders in the South Sudan People's defence Forces (SSPDF), retired generals with memory of SPLA/SSPDF transition and their (civilian) counterparts at the national and state levels. There will also be groups in the region that are in itself an issue - people that are part of the political economy are closely tied to military networks-people like businessmen. Some other actors include representatives of civil society and international actors dealing with the Security Sector Reform (SSR) and peace processes (e.g., RJMEC, CTSAMVM, UN agencies). Their prized perceptions will help piece together career trajectories, loyalty perceptions, and military-linked economic networks, all the same, fundamental forces in creating the military's role in state-building in South Sudan (Warner, 2016; de Waal, 2015; Jok, 2012).

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs): This study will employ Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) for engaging civilians in discussions around the function of military governance, security, and everyday life. These will be a gathering of diverse groups—elders from the community, youth with differing affiliations, women's associations, displaced persons, and local administration. In the process of this research, attention will be given for inclusivity and creation of possibilities for the shared mean-making and group dynamics.

A total of nine FGDs will be conducted, including three in each region: Equatoria, Upper Nile, and Bahr el Ghazal. The discussions will be conducted in major urban centres within the regions, such as Juba and state capitals, Malakal, Wau, Bentiu, to reflect both the central and the regional dynamics. The design thus captures variations in civilian experiences and understandings in different contexts of South Sudan regarding the SSPDF as a coercive actor and economic operator (LeRiche, 2018; Nyadera, 2018; Watson, 2016).

Documentary Review: The research will review legal frameworks, peace agreements, institutional reports, and scholarly literature in order to triangulate an ideal military-

professionalization in the midst of reality of militarized patronage in South Sudan, looking at legal frameworks, peace agreements, institutional reports, and scholarly literature. Major texts that will be reviewed include Transitional Constitution (2011), SPLA Act (2009), and SSPDF White Papers in order to understand the intended control of the sovereign state over civilian party in Chapter II of the R-ARCSS (2018) (Weber, 1946; Huntington, 1957). Chapter II of the R-ARCSS (2018) will be analyzed for force integration and security sector reform (Nyadera, 2018; Jok, 2012), while budgets, UN Panel of Experts reports, and The Sentry investigations will highlight military-linked commercial interests (de Waal, 2015; Warner, 2016). Comparison with other cases like Bosnia and Tanzania will anchor South Sudan within wider reflections on militarized state-building (Bryden & Hänggi, 2005; LeRiche, 2018).

Data Analysis

The data collected from interviews, focus group discussions, and document reviews, will be analyzed thematically. This process is typical for qualitative exploratory research as it allows to identify recurring patterns, meanings, and relationships from diverse sources at once. Transcripts from interviews and FGDs will be coded inductively to capture themes like loyalty, patronage, ethnic mobilization, and military economics.

Documentation will be used to triangulate institutional reports, academic literature, peace agreements, and legal frameworks along with primary data, in order to assure the strength of the validation and capability for verification and consistency of findings. Comparing through multiple case studies which shall be Greater Upper Nile, Greater Bahr el Ghazal, Greater Equatoria, to elucidate on the countervailing fundamentals of institutional dynamics and the state-building exercises.

Validity, Reliability, and Ethics

Rigor in qualitative research has to be ensured with credibility, including elements of triangulation and member-checking for ensuring validity and reliability. Transferability is very important to the researchers for the purpose of making meaning with thick descriptions. Also, dependability, confirmability, and researcher's rigor--all ascertained with statutory compliance to national and international ethical conventions--define the vogue in this study.

It is essential that ethical considerations be taken into account given that the research was to take place in areas affected by conflict. Consent will be obtained, paying due consideration to fixtures of both verbal and written consent forms, depending on the participant's level of literacy, and the security pound. Anonymity will also be safeguarded. Hence coded numbers will be assigned for anonymity purposes. In every activity, and each one of the notes taken, the core principle of not doing any harm will be applied. Proper security analysis and subsequent implementation of proper measures depending on the highest risks from the survey sites will also be in place. Safety for the researcher will be of paramount importance as well as protection for the participants.

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DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS

KEY INFORMANT INTERVIEWS (KII) GUIDE

SECTION A: Introduction

My name is SEKWAT, Aromeo James Sworo, and I am a PhD candidate in Political Science at the University of Dar es Salaam. I am conducting research on “The Role of the Military in State-Building in South Sudan” as part of my doctoral thesis. The main objective of this study is to critically examine the role that military institutional dynamics have played on the state-building process in the Republic of South Sudan, focusing on a transformation process from a liberation movement to a professional national defence force. I have identified you as a key participant for this assignment, but your participation is voluntary and there is no punishment for refusing to participate. If you consent to the interview, then we can proceed.

SECTION B: Sample identification

Date: ____/____/____

Start time: ____/____ Finish time: ____/____

Region..... State

Name of the Respondent..... (OPTIONAL)

Position.....

Institution

Gender

SECTION C: Professionalization and Institutional Transition

1. How would you describe the transition of the SPLA into the SSPDF since the 2005 CPA?
2. In your view, what are the primary challenges in transforming a liberation movement into a professional national army?
3. How are recruitment and promotion handled within your unit? To what extent do ethnic or political affiliations influence these processes?
4. What has been the impact of Security Sector Reform (SSR) and DDR programs on the unity and professionalism of the force?
5. How do you perceive the command-and-control structure? Is it centralized, or are there “parallel” chains of command?

SECTION D: Civil-Military Relations and Governance

1. How often do military commanders participate in civilian administrative decision-making in your jurisdiction?
2. Can you provide examples where military logic or security priorities have overridden civilian policy objectives?
3. What is the role of former military officers now serving in civilian administrative positions? How does their background influence their governance style?
4. How do you manage potential conflicts between civilian local authorities and military commanders on the ground?
5. To what extent is the civilian budget influenced by military requirements or direct military intervention?

SECTION E: Military, Political Economy and Power Dynamics

1. How does the military sustain itself beyond the national budget, and what role do military-linked entities play in sectors such as oil, mining, or trade?
2. In what ways do these commercial interests affect the discipline, focus, and professionalism of the military as a national defense institution?
3. How does the military coordinate with civilian institutions, particularly the Ministry of Finance, regarding its commercial or resource-linked activities?
4. To what extent do profits from military-linked enterprises influence political loyalty, elite patronage, and the stability of the current government, including the implementation of the Revitalized Peace Agreement (R-ARCSS)?
5. How does military control of economic resources impact opportunities for civilian-owned businesses and broader private sector development in South Sudan?

Thank you for your cooperation!

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION (FGD) GUIDE

SECTION A: Introduction

My name is **SEKWAT, Aromeo James Sworo**, and I am a PhD candidate in Political Science at the University of Dar es Salaam. I am conducting research on “**The Role of the Military in State-Building in South Sudan**” as part of my doctoral thesis. The main objective of this study is to critically examine the role that military institutional dynamics have played on the state-building process in the Republic of South Sudan, focusing on a transformation process from a liberation movement to a professional national defence force. You have been identified as a key participant for this discussion because of your knowledge and experience relevant to the study. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and there are no consequences if you choose not to take part. You are free to withdraw at any time or decline to answer any question. If you agree to participate, we will proceed with the focus group discussion.

SECTION B: Sample identification

Date: _____ / _____ / _____

Start time: ____ / ____ Finish time: ____ / ____

Region..... State

Name of the Respondent..... (OPTIONAL)

Position.....

Institution

Gender

SECTION A: Professionalization and Institutional Transition

- How do you view the transition of the SPLA into the SSPDF since the 2005 CPA?
- What challenges exist in transforming a liberation movement into a professional national army?
- To what extent do recruitment and promotion reflect merit versus ethnic or political affiliations?

SECTION B: Civil-Military Relations and Governance

- How do military officials influence civilian governance and policymaking at national and state levels?
- Can you share examples where military priorities have overridden civilian policy objectives?
- What role do former military officers play when serving in civilian positions?

SECTION D: Military, Political Economy and Power Dynamics

- In what ways do commercial profits from military-linked enterprises influence political loyalty and the stability of the current government?
- How does the commercial interests of the military affect the implementation of the Revitalized Peace Agreement (R-ARCSS)?
- Does the control of economic resources by military elites create a barrier to entry for civilian-owned private businesses?

Thank you for your cooperation!

UNIVERSITY OF DAR ES SALAAM

Directorate of Postgraduate Studies

APPENDIX II – APPROVAL FORM FOR RESEARCH PROPOSAL

Candidate Information

- Name: SEKWAT, Aromeo James Sworo
- Registration Number: 2023-07-00275
- Programme: *Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Political Science, by Thesis*
- Department: Department of Political Science and Public Administration
- College/School: College of Social Sciences

Proposed Research Title: THE ROLE OF MILITARY IN STATE-BUILDING IN SOUTH SUDAN

Supervisor's Endorsement I have reviewed the candidate's research proposal and confirm that it meets the required academic standards for submission to the Departmental Postgraduate Committee.

- Supervisor's Name: Dr. Richard Bonaventura Mbunda
- Signature:
- Date: 31st March 2026

Departmental Postgraduate Committee Chairperson's Endorsement I hereby certify that the above candidate's proposal has been reviewed and approved by the Departmental Postgraduate Committee.

- Chairperson's Name: Professor Mohammed Ali Bakari
- Signature:
- Date: 17th April 2026

Candidate's Declaration I confirm that this proposal is my original work and has been prepared in accordance with the University of Dar es Salaam's regulations and guidelines for postgraduate programmes.

- Candidate's Name: SEKWAT, Aromeo James Sworo
- Signature:
- Date: 31st March 2026